

BEYOND FORGOTTEN

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The world moves on with its hurried pace,
While I am here,
Trying to remember your voice,
Calling my name.

Isn't strange, unjust, and unfair
How seasons change?
While I am here,
Clinging to phantom memories of your warm embrace.

They say time will gently dull the blade
That every wound will heal from ache.
But I'd rather not let this heavy grief fade
If it means losing pieces of you, gone and breakaway.

So let this heartbreak stay,
Lock this penance inside my chest.
Because within tears I shed everyday.
The echo of your voice is manifest.

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